

Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) for Urban Restoration in the Centre of Athens

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Abstract

In the case of restoration of the urban environment in the centre of Athens in Greece, we use the WTP method to compute approximate external economies. The preservation/restoration of natural environment is frequently entailing excessive cost (paid by people through taxation), while it is a source of additional income for both, the State and the people, due to tourism. Since the evaluation of this good cannot be in market terms, we apply here in a modified version of the Contingent Valuation Method (CVM), which is used in Experimental Economics in order to investigate the significance that people put on this good and how much they might be willing to pay (WTP) for supporting activities concerning the preservation/restoration of the urban environment of the centre of Athens.

Key-Words: environmental impact, Willingness to Pay (WTP), Willingness to Accept (WTA), Contingent Valuation Method (CVM), Environmental impact, Logit Model, Parametric Approach, Non-Parametric Approach, Probit Model

Introduction

The purpose of the paper is to present a modified model of an internalizing external costs caused by the operation of a manufacturing unit in conjunction with the new reality created. The environment is characterized as a public good. Public goods are goods that provide benefits for society as a whole or part of it, usually regardless of whether the individual people are willing to pay to have these benefits. All entities, whether individuals or businesses or public agencies, have some financial resources with which they seek to achieve specific objectives (e.g. profit maximization).

In our analysis we consider the natural environment as a public good and environmental pollution as an external economy fails the price mechanism to internalize. In all three cases, the approach of foreign trade was with the VTP method and calculated the external costs generated by the degradation of the environment from the responses of respondents in monetary units. Respondents answered without knowing it was the environment to its original condition and not expect it to return to its original form. The quality of the clean environment and therefore the valuation of

foreign economic burden caused by contamination with personal criteria and the personal endorsement of the value of that public good. In the case of archaeological monuments, residents have built their buildings. In case of three areas, respondents have developed an urban way of life around the areas. In the case of industrial units, residents have supported throughout the local economy on them.

The initial state of the environment are unknown and undefined. Also the urban environment are altering the original state cannot be determined. Human works and buildings create new values in the region and therefore the external costs can be measured only with the expected quality of the environment and is not lost. Allowances, taxation and value of land use are calculated solely on the expected image of the landscape. Therefore, the Pareto optimal socioeconomic lines status is defined according to the new form of environment created after the regeneration of areas and not according to the initial state of the environment. Also in Kaldor compensation should be determined based on the economic valuation of public goods by their own people, who judge based on expectations rather than on the past. The expected form natural environment varies from respondent to respondent and its approach to social welfare units can only be done through alternative scenarios best and worst scenario.

In any case, the society wants to reach the minimum point of the charge received from the pollution and what can be achieved by the 'invisible hand', but the regulation and government intervention. History has shown that the charge received by the society because of pollution varies with the socioeconomic status of citizens. The more low-income residents are more elastic is the loss of the urban environment. The elasticity of citizens deprived or not the urban environment is measurable size.

Methods

During the last three decades there has been growing interest in developing methods for assessing the preferences (of experts, stake holders, community/organization members, independent individuals) for environmental quality. Among them, the Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) is frequently applied to (i) economic valuation of environmental projects or works/activities (planned or in operation) with a significant environmental impact and (ii) damage assessment after environmental accidents, i.e., after incidents that deteriorate environmental quality. This method is heavily relied on survey-based estimation of (i) willingness to pay (WTP), which is the maximum amount of money a person would be willing to pay, sacrifice or exchange for a public good, and (ii) willingness to accept (WTA), which is the minimum amount of money a person would be willing to accept in order to abandon a good. WTP is bounded by income while WTA is potentially unlimited. Whether WTP or WTA is appropriate, depends on the prior distribution of property rights and the direction of change under consideration. The Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) is a survey-based technique, frequently used in Experimental Economics, especially useful for the valuation of non-market resources/goods/services, and cultural heritage objects (of aesthetic, historic, scientific or social value), such as conservation of monumental remains and preservation of the physical and anthropogenic environment [1,2]. The current endowment of an environmental commodity is often taken as implying legal right to an increase in the quantity of an environmental amenity and should be valued using WTP whereas reductions should be valued using WTA. If

WTP and WTA were evaluated at the same level of utility, they should be identical, but empirical evidence consistently demonstrates that WTA may exceed WTP by an order of magnitude [1-3]. Therefore, WTP provides a purchase price, relevant for valuing the proposed gain of the good while WTA provides a selling price, relevant for valuing the proposed loss of the good. According to Classic Economic Theory, a significant difference between WTP and WTA should not occur, on condition that there is (i) no transaction cost, (ii) perfect information about goods/services and corresponding prices, (iii) no income effect, (iv) a market that engenders truthful revelation of preferences. Although these conditions were generally met in several economic experiments that used inexpensive market goods with readily available substitutes, the ratios WTA/WTP obtained were significantly greater than unity. This result was attributed to the fact that participants in these experiments lacked market experience [3].

The aim of this work is to present a dynamic methodological framework for evaluating environmental impact caused by human activities by means of the CVM, referring to alternative routes of investigation and including successive levels of information granularity in continuous interaction with a dedicated local Knowledge Base (KB) created ad hoc. Results from three case studies are also presented.

In case that the CVM is applied for monumental remains, certain specific problems arise, because (i) the 'good' under examination has a subjective value, dependent on the cultural level of each reviewee, (ii) the intangibles associated with this 'good' are related to the present political behaviour of each individual as regards his/her attitude to the local authorities or the central government, (iii) as a result, the answers may be biased, a matter that becomes evident only after final statistical processing, thus calling for supplementary information, possibly by means of an additional post-questionnaire, and (iv) the adopted/developed (for elicitation of people's WTP) technique itself should be revised (possibly by means of a meta-questionnaire) by the same group of experts who processed the answers in order to improve the questionnaire and store it into a dedicated Knowledge Base (KB) for future usage, since each monument is unique and the results coming from examining quasi-similar cases are of limited value.

The aim of this study is to provide policy-makers with much needed information on the economic value of the benefits generated by the sustainable management of the street. Conducting pilot research involving small numbers of 4, so as to determine some basic parameters, which could help to formulate some of the questions in the questionnaire

In the contingent valuation part of the questionnaire, participants were asked to determine the amount of money that each respondent was willing to pay for 12 months to help maintain or even improve the state of each area near the street. Taking into consideration that the subsidy which was given by the government and the local authorities can't increase.

Members of the public were randomly intercepted in city and town centres, cafes and markets, and were interviewed face-to-face. The sample size was 240 questionnaires, consisted of 52.5% women and 47.5% men and the majority of people age was

between 26 and 35 years old. This was put down to the fact that young people were more willing to participate in the survey.

In addition, survey respondents were educated to a higher level, 36,50% had finished high school and 28,5% had attended university. The majority of survey respondents belonged to the intermediate income class. These results can be explained by the fact that most of the respondents came from urban areas, where education and full-time employment levels are higher. About half of the sample lives or work in close proximity of that areas. However average willingness to pay does not differ significantly between respondents of close proximity or of no proximity.

When respondents were asked to assign a level of importance to the protection of the area on the 3-point response scale, 93,75% considered it very important to protect the urban environment, 13. 2% said protection was enough important and only 5% thought that the preservation of the area was slightly important.

The questionnaire examined, among other factors, the attitudes of citizens towards the city's environmental problems. In addition, the majority of participants' report that the main reason of environmental problems arise from the failure or limited capacity of governments and local authorities.

Furthermore, the WTP question was asked the respondent to select an option from a range of values, Seven values were presented, ranging from 0 € to 25 € and the seventh option was opened (Figure 1). The proportion of all respondents who expressed a willingness to pay some amount was 90% .The descriptive statistics provide helpful information on the percent frequency of the WTP-value: 10% of the sample suggested WTP=0 €, 50% agreed with WTP=1-10 €, 35% accepted WTP=11-25€, 26% mentioned WTP=26-50 €.

Based on these questions can make a regression analysis giving an equation of willingness to pay the respondent made specific linear regression analysis for correlation of question 11(amount WTP to classes – dependent variable) and all other questions (independent variables).

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

where N is the number of observations, y is the dependent variable, $\bar{y}$ is the mean of the y values, and $\hat{y}$ is the value predicted by the model. R2 is the determination coefficient that ranges from 0 to 1. According to the Efron's R2:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{\pi}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\pi}$ = model predicted probabilities, the dependent variable in a logistic regression is not continuous while the predicted value (a probability) is. MacFadden introduced the log likelihood of the intercept model.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\ln \hat{L}(M_{Full})}{\ln \hat{L}(M_{Intercept})} \quad (2)$$

where MFull is the model with predictors, MIntercept is the model without predictors, and $\hat{L}$ is the estimated likelihood. A likelihood falls between 0 and 1, so the log of likelihood is less than, or equal to, zero. If a model has a very low likelihood, then the log of the likelihood will have a larger magnitude than the log of a more likely model.

Cox and Snell present the R2 as a transformation of the $2 \ln [L(M_{Intercept}) / L(M_{Full})]$ statistic that is used to determine the convergence of a logistic regression.

$$R^2 = 1 - \left\{ \frac{L(M_{Intercept})}{L(M_{Full})} \right\}^{\frac{2}{N}} \quad (3)$$

Note that Cox & Snell's pseudo-R2 has a maximum value that is not 1; if the full model predicts the outcome perfectly and has a likelihood of 1, then we have

$$1 - L(M_{Intercept})^{\frac{2}{N}} < 1. \quad (4)$$

Nagelkerke, Cragg and Uhler, adjust Cox & Snell's R2 so that the range of possible values extends to 1.

$$R^2 = \frac{1 - \left\{ \frac{L(M_{Intercept})}{L(M_{Full})} \right\}^{\frac{2}{N}}}{1 - L(M_{Intercept})^{\frac{2}{N}}} \quad (5)$$

R^2	Area 1	Area 2	Area 3
Cox and Snell	0.888	0,746	0,705
Nagelkerke	0.852	0,837	0,766
McFadden	0.877	0,618	0,481

The non-linear regression model we used is the Probit and the Logit ones. Probit is a popular specification for an ordinal or a binary response model that employs a link function. In this model, the response variable y is binary and may represent a certain condition. A generalized form of this model is the following:

$$\Pr(y = 1/x) = \Phi(x'\beta) \quad (6)$$

where $\Pr$ denotes probability and Φ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution. The parameters β are typically estimated by maximum likelihood. There exists an auxiliary random variable:

$$y^* = x'\beta + \varepsilon, \text{ where error } \varepsilon \in N(0,1) \quad (7)$$

Then y can be considered as an indicator for whether this latent variable is positive:

$$y = 1_{\{y^* > 0\}} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y^* > 0, \text{ i.e., } -\varepsilon < x'\beta \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The Logit model gives the logistic function:

$$f(z) = \frac{e^z}{e^z + 1} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}} \quad (9)$$

where the variable z is usually defined as:

$$z = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \dots + \beta_k x_k \quad (10)$$

where β_0 is the intercept and $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_k$ are the regression coefficients of $x_1, \dots, x_k$, respectively. Actually, R^2 , the coefficient of determination, is the relative power of the Probit and the Logit model.

For the Lake of Kastoria, the coefficients are statistically significant are those variables X_9 , X_{12} , X_{14} , X_{19} and X_{28} . The constant (1164) is the price at which the straight line (least squares) intersects the vertical axis of coordinates. The model that is adapted to these data is:

$$WTP = 1.164 - 0.279X_9 + 0.82X_{12} - 0.147X_{14} - 0.173X_{19} + 0.113X_{28}$$

More specifically, the amount will be paid by the respondent (WTP) change significantly when you consider that: The protection of the urban environment is very important (X_9), increase the amount you will pay if you lived here (X_{12}), the amount received by the respondent as compensation reduced (X_{14}), the respondent has property, (X_{19}) and the income is high compared with the average (X_{28}).

To address the problem of violation of normality, a determination of the amount of financial contribution (WTP), after ranking the data into classes. Specifically, the division into classes is as follows:

- Class1:0€
- Class2:1-10€
- Class3:11-25€
- Class 4: 26-50 €

For the Area 1, the coefficients are statistically significant are those variables X_{1A} , X_{4A} , X_6 , X_{10} and X_{12} . The constant (0.182) is the price at which the straight line (least squares) intersects the vertical axis of coordinates. The above table contains estimates of the model. The model that is adapted to these data is:

$$WTP = 0.182 - 0.228X_{1A} + 0.205X_{4A} + 0.367X_6 - 0.183X_{10} + 0.607X_{12}$$

More specifically, the amount will be paid by the respondent (WTP) change significantly when: The frequency of visits is high (X_{1A}), Does a significant problem the appearance of the area (X_{4A}), Strive to be paid by the competent bodies is not satisfactory (X_6), Strengthen energy to improve the lake is organic farming (X_{10}), increasing the amount of the contribution (WTP) if lived here (X_{12}).

According to the frequency histogram (Histogram) the financial contribution of the sample (WTP), the distribution of the amounts designated as right-skewed (positive asymmetry). This means that at the right price there is a shortfall in relation to left, and so the distribution is not normal.

For the Area 2, the coefficients are statistically significant are those variables X_3 , X_{12} and X_{24} . The constant (2016) is the price at which the straight line (least squares) intersects the vertical axis of coordinates. The model that is adapted to these data is:
$$WTP = 2.016 - 0.271X_3 + 0.774X_{12} - 0.437X_{24}$$

More specifically, the amount will be paid by the respondent (WTP) change significantly when considering that: The environmental condition of the area is poor (X_3). Increase the amount of the contribution (WTP) if they lived here (X_{12}), Marital Status Married states (X_{24}). We observe that the improvement of the area, the estimated average annual contribution for all respondents is 8.22 € (median 5 €), while the amount of 5 € is the most common offer (central tendency). According to the frequency histogram (Histogram) the financial contribution of the sample (WTP), the distribution of the amounts designated as right-skewed (positive asymmetry). This means that at the right price there is a shortfall in relation to left, and so the distribution is not normal.

We conclude that According to survey results the willingness to pay (WTP) is nearly identical for the three study areas. The highest WTP is the area of Area 2 13.16 € while it has the smallest percentage (10%) denied contribution from the people surveyed. Second comes the region of Area 1 with the amount of 10.14 € and the third region of Area 3, the amount of 8.22 €. Survey results show that the protection and enhancement of wetlands is a latent economic value. Now its value is confirmed not only by the intrinsic self-worth inherent as good, which is enjoyed by our senses, but according to modern principles of economic theory, which applied, wetlands can be viewed as a commodity (public good) that can be costed on a fairly large sum.

Conclusion

The survey results show that the protection and enhancement of wetlands is a latent economic value. Now its value is confirmed not only by the intrinsic self-worth as inherent good that we enjoy with our senses, but according to modern principles of Economic Theory, which applied, wetlands can be viewed as a commodity which can be costed on a fairly large sum.

The response of the sample to improve the wetland was satisfactory, since a significant proportion of respondents, who are willing to contribute on a voluntary basis, an amount even though surveys of this type are something completely new for the greek reality. From this survey is very important to understand the social importance of wetlands. It should also be understood that the protection is a first class resource for many areas, but also through attracting visitors and qualitative characteristics of the regions will have to pole of attraction and overall development.

For these reasons, although it costs to maintain wetlands for residents and local authorities, it would begin to believe that it will provide a basis for development than

others. The interest of the residents for maintenance and improvement of wetlands is a message for further mobilization of the local community. At the same time, is given a large responsibility on local authorities by the residents themselves, as most protest denials based on powers has the municipality to conserve wetlands.

Since education is a crucial factor that increases WTP medium / long term, future research should be aimed at schools, colleges and universities in the region to increase the value of non-use and to obtain useful information related to awareness of young people. Research using the hypothetical assessment has been used successfully overseas and now recognized as a valid argument. The survey can be a powerful tool in the hands of local and regional authorities for claiming generous funding for the purpose mentioned above.

In conclusion, our analysis shows that social science research can provide useful information about the complex issues of environmental policy, such as restoring urban ecosystem. The analysis of policy for such cases is particularly difficult because these systems provide multiple, interrelated services vary depending on the type of urban area, location and other factors. The work presented here has proved a useful integrated tool for determining the realistic cognitive burden on stakeholders and third parties.

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